

Challenges Encountered by Human Resource Management in Implementing a Culture of Innovation in Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality in Eastern Cape, South Africa

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In municipal governments, innovation is becoming more widely acknowledged as a key factor in boosting operational effectiveness and service delivery. This article discusses the obstacles faced by Human Resource Management in adopting innovations within the Eastern Cape region of Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality (BCMM). This article aims to determine and evaluate the main obstacles faced by Human Resource Management (HRM) when introducing innovation in local government in the Eastern Cape, investigate the effects caused by such obstacles on the operational efficiency and provision of services of municipalities and recommend techniques that HRM departments may adopt for overcoming these obstacles while effectively embrace innovative practices. The data was acquired from 10 participants from the HRM division and was evaluated utilizing thematic data analysis approaches. The study findings revealed that HRM in BCMM encountered numerous challenges such as inadequate resources, reluctance to change, a shortage of appropriate skills, as well as a fragile organizational culture. These problems are hindering the municipality's capability to successfully implement innovative HR practices, eventually impacting its potential to enhance the provision of services. The article's conclusion offers suggestions for resolving these issues, highlighting the significance of organizational culture, leadership, and capacity building in fostering effective innovation in local government.

Keywords: Innovation, human resource management, service delivery, buffalo city metropolitan municipality

Local government is vital to the provision of basic amenities to communities and is at the heart of regional development. However, in South Africa, many municipalities, notably in the Eastern Cape, are grappling with challenges relating to inefficient operations, mismanagement of funds, and service delivery delays (Auditor General Report, 2023). Innovation is regarded as a crucial solution to these difficulties, but applying innovative techniques requires significant human resource support. By attracting and developing people, implementing new technology, and encouraging staff adaptation, Human Resource Management (HRM) in municipalities is at the forefront of establishing creative cultures (Hartley, Parker, & Beashel, 2019). Despite these obligations, Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality (BCMM) HRM has major challenges that impede innovation. The municipality is progressively redefining the manner in which services are delivered to citizens

through innovation and many innovative projects, with HRM having a significant part to play employing diverse techniques to make these innovations succeed (Fan, Meng, & Wei, 2020).

In order to guarantee efficient service delivery and governance, South African local governments are subject to a number of rules and regulations. The Eastern Cape is one of the country's poorest provinces, confronting particular obstacles to development, such as unemployment, rural poverty, and an acute shortage of infrastructure (Zindi, 2024). Innovation in local government procedures, technology, and personnel management is crucial to tackling these fundamental challenges. The role of HRM is vital for fostering innovation in municipalities, particularly by implementing new management techniques, integrating digital tools, and guaranteeing a qualified and engaged personnel (Mhlanga, Ndhlovu, & Hofisi, 2021).

In South Africa, service delivery challenges are common in communities throughout the country as citizens are doubting the capabilities of local municipalities in developing innovative ways of providing services (Zindi & Ndhlovu, 2023). The BCMM is unable to carry out this function due to several obstacles, such as inadequate budget for training and development, opposition from management and staff, outdated policies, and a lack of technology infrastructure (Danielle & Masilela, 2020).

These challenges contribute to the slow rate of modernization in local government, significantly blocking the ability of municipalities to satisfy their service delivery requirements. Understanding these problems is critical for increasing HRM competence and promoting local government performance. Human

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Resource Management in BCMM is failing to embrace new innovative approaches that may enhance service delivery, effectiveness as well as responsibility (Arundel, Bloch, & Ferguson, 2019). It is against this background that this article examines the primary challenges faced by HRM in BCMM and provides an analysis of potential strategies to overcome these challenges.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify and analyse the key challenges faced by Human Resource Management in implementing innovation in local government within the Eastern Cape.
- To examine the impact of these challenges on the performance and service delivery of municipalities.
- To propose strategies that HRM departments can adopt to overcome these challenges and successfully implement innovative practices.

The Development of Innovation in Local Government

In South Africa, public sector reforms originated in 1994, marked by numerous innovative changes, such as the transition from a highly centralized command and control system to a more decentralized structure across national, provincial, and local government levels (Dam & Siang, 2020). The National Development Plan strengthens this decentralisation and goes further to make a bold call for devolving power to the provincial the local government. Such decentralization of powers was supposed to ensure that each sphere of government must come up with innovative and novel means of accomplishing its task and performing its duties. Since 1994, the paradigm shift from public sector reform has developed from democratization to transformation of the state apparatus (1994-2004) to the establishment of a developmental state (2005-2013) (Gasela, 2022). There has been tremendous innovation in organisational design, human resource management, public policy and law-making coming from the new Constitution. However, several scholars noted that South Africa currently needs human resources that can spur innovation and a cohesive model of public sector transformation (South African Government, 2021).

The Department of Public Service Administration is primarily responsible for establishing guidelines and standards for public reforms and innovations in local government (South African Government, 2021). This ensures that service delivery, human resources, institutional development and governance efforts are receptive to the needs of the population. In recent years, this responsibility has advanced beyond updating and modernizing the Public Service into creating and implementing frameworks and policies (Chen, Walker, & Sawhney, 2020) that enhance service delivery, strengthen monitoring and assessment, and offer implementation help to guarantee compliance (Sicakyuz, 2023). Innovative public services can empower public institutions to provide value-for-money services.

Like the rest of the globe, South Africa is challenged with hard social-economic, political challenges and innovation. To combat this threat, a comprehensive strategy involving robust cooperation between the public and commercial sectors at all levels national, provincial, and local is required (Houtgraaf, 2023). In order to provide services to people, such a collaboration has to develop creative solutions. Some municipalities, including the Water and

Sanitation unit of the eThekweni Municipality, have collaborated with the World Bank and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation in an effort to encourage them to think out of the box (South African Government, 2021). They have to employ modified shipping containers as public ablution blocks as an innovative solution to cope with sanitary challenges in the informal settlements, where it benefited an estimated 600 households as of 2015 (Arundel, Bloch, & Ferguson, 2019). Moreover, the City of Johannesburg adopted an electronic procurement system to streamline purchasing processes and promote transparency in procurement transactions (Zindi, 2024).

Furthermore, another example of a municipality that has come up with an innovative idea to better the lives of its people through its digital technology initiative named Project Isizwe in the City of Tshwane with its Wi-FiTV (Plantinga & Adams, 2021). It is vital to recognize that internet connectivity must be treated as a basic service. The City of Tshwane moved on to offer another creative platform called DigiMbizo, which is a digital izimbizo that national government embraces nationally to communicate with communities face-to-face. Tshwane citizens may participate in Imbizo with their mayor in the comfort of their own homes thanks to the DigiMbizo. Using the DigiMbizo, the local government can connect with communities that generally fail to attend conventional forums (Mergel, 2018; Clausen, Demircioglu, & Alsos, 2020). In particular, the DigiMbizo is assisting the municipality keep track of feedback from the public, which also enhances the speed of addressing concerns through the hashtag #DigiMbizo or #AskRamokgopa on Twitter. To overcome obstacles in local government, innovation is essential (some of the most innovative ideas are coming from the most rural parts of our country) (Gaskell, 2020:2).

Innovation and Service Delivery in Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality

Lack of innovation sparked by HRM strategy is one of the local government's biggest problems. The BCMM is trying to improve leadership skills at political and administrative levels, and employees' skills to promote innovation in the municipality. Byrne (2021) pointed out that financial and human resources are necessary for innovation to take place. The HRM strategies, such as workforce planning, recruiting, selecting, rewarding, induction, training, progression, and budget allocation within BCMM are the key drivers of employee performance and innovativeness (BCMM Draft Integrated Development Plan Review, 2022/2023). There is an absence of research into modern approaches to innovation in local government in South Africa, while it is the sector of government that operates under pressure to implement innovation (Levy, Hirsch, Naidoo, & Nxele, 2021). BCMM is still depending on spreadsheets and obsolete legacy databases to hold employees' data and accessing these databases is time consuming, wasteful, mistakes in the data and often incomplete data consequently harming workforce planning (Marabella, 2019; Fan et al., 2020).

This absence of inventiveness and innovativeness has culminated in scarcity of personnel in critical positions, for example, in 2023, there were 158 fully financed unfilled positions in BCMM. Poor workforce planning, recruitment, selection, and budget allocation in BCMM are to blame for the lack of qualified personnel in key roles (Danielle & Masilela, 2020). Other municipalities are inventing new ways to help with staffing planning, hiring and selecting workers, for example, the CivicHR in Manhattan local government in New York

City, which is sophisticated, yet uncomplicated to use, web-based human resource platform built particularly for local government. CivicHR expedites the hiring and workforce planning process, finds and chooses the best applicant fast, and offers the greatest training and development initiatives (Technology Evaluation Centers, 2025). Thus, it can be claimed that lack of innovative HRM strategies has led to lack of creative talents required for local government to carry out its constitutional mandate (Barwani, 2019). Due to a lack of personnel and a system that provides funding for individuals who are innovative in carrying out their duties in novel ways, the execution of numerous projects has been lagging behind in municipal plans and, more importantly, behind the growing expectations of citizens (Dikotla, 2019).

Thus, it can be stated that inventive workforce strategy and workers' creative abilities are not evident in BCMM as the city is fighting to come up with competent people, which may result in novel methods of performing their responsibilities (Barwani, 2019). Such a lack of innovation affects service delivery such as water, power, garbage management, and infrastructure, which has led to uprisings two and half decades since the democratic dispensation (Carpio, 2018). This raised the need to assess the way HRM strategies in BCMM are mainly concerned with workforce planning, which paves the way for recruitment and selection of creative personnel, rewarding those with inventive intellectuals, induction, training and development, funding allocation and what kind of organizational atmosphere exists in BCMM as these constitute the driving forces of creative thinking. James (2021) mentions that there is a beneficial relationship between HRM practices and innovation that tries to increase the manner in which people perform their responsibilities.

Guiding Theory- Social Learning Theory

Albert Bandura introduced the Social Learning Theory in 1963. According to Bandura, learning is an intellectual endeavour that often takes place in a social context through personal guidance and observation (Davey, 2015). Thus, Johnson (2014) postulates that learning can be described as "a shift in cognitive processes that creates the ability to demonstrate various behaviours that occurs as a result of observing others". The basic idea is that much of the development in human cognition is clarified by the interplay of internal personal elements in the form of intellectual, emotive and physiological processes, behaviour and environmental events which can be triggered or impacted by certain conditions (Nabavi, 2014). This idea is founded on the premise that people gain knowledge through everyday interactions that occur in a social setting, be it at the job, community or in a home environment (Edinyang, 2016).

As stated by Carpio (2018) globalization, cutting-edge technology advancements, demographics, and climate change are all contributing to the world's rapid and significant transformation and adjustment. The nature of jobs and skills required in the labour market, as well as the impact on employment composition, are only a few of the issues that accompany these developments. This study is well-suited to the Social Learning Theory, which holds that people learn by watching others and paying attention to what they are doing. This indicates that attention, retention, and replication can be included in HRM's development and training strategy to make sure that employees are paying attention throughout training (Jensen, 2020). Employees can remember the information and abilities they acquire through training. More significantly, when faced with a task or circumstance that requires the skills that they have learned, they may use those abilities and knowledge to be inventive and creative. This can be effectively

motivated by leadership, which is one of the elements of innovation. The leader must set an example that encourages innovation so that their followers will also learn by doing, paying attention, and observing their leaders (Kumari & Singh, 2018; Austin, 2021).

Conceptualising Innovation

Innovations can be idea-generation propelled by curiosity and diverse thinking that can be employed to attain a goal or address a challenge (Brady, 2017:4). Thus, innovation can be delineated and understood in various ways contingent upon the context one is operating from, as claimed by scholars such as Attour and Chaupain-Guillot (2020). This is true because bad times may lead to key answers or give the setting for creativity and change, even change that would not have been explored or believed practicable in different circumstances (Jacobson & Sowa, 2016:125).

Innovation has been contextualized and seen in this study as a learning process that can lead to the emergence of something new that may be facilitated or hindered by various local government circumstances arising from the work of organizational actors represented by HRM professionals. The South African public sector is plagued with dwindling funds and increased demand for enhanced service performance (Cinar, Trott, & Simms, 2019) which requires public sector changes in the form of creative HRM strategies to address all these issues. Of the various strategies available to people to develop this future, innovation has a greater prospect and has proved to provide in some circumstances and fail in comparable prospects.

For every tale of monumental innovation, there is another wasted opportunity. This is why innovation has turned out to be a term for numerous businesses and people, and even though doubt appears progressively widespread, no one repudiates that those final modifications in society are through marvellous innovations and innovative perception (Medley, 2020).

Importance of Innovation in Local Government

Enhancing the government's innovation provides considerable benefits when it comes to excellent quality, efficiency and reliable provision of services. On top of competency and effectiveness of government sector innovation, the extent of the prospective also hinges on the influence of the municipal government service provision (Evans, 2018). The contribution of fostering a culture of innovation will have far-fetched benefits, that include agility, change creation, citizen/client focus, advancement of workplace learning and information technology as detailed below. Innovation promotes the cooperation of all sectors of society, including government, business sector, people, and partners, and this will aid in meeting community requirements and demands (Mariani, Eggers, Chew, & O'Leary, 2021).

Figure 1

Shows the Importance of Innovation

Note Source: Compiled by the Authors.

Adaptability

An organization must prioritize developing its workforce's capacity to respond to changing circumstances if it is to adapt to change. Training and skill development are the focus of HRM, and more specifically, HRD. This might consist of giving workers an opportunity to up-skill to enhance their abilities and expertise in innovation, build their skill set and capacities (Koziol-Nadolna & Beyer, 2021). It can entail maintaining documentation of employees' abilities and experience to ascertain and solve the demand for innovation and disperse that innovation in the organization where it is desired. Organizations will be able to absorb new information in the unstable environment of today if they are always learning (Demircioglu, 2017).

Create Change

Examining how an organization operates and advocating for changes to its structure, procedures, culture, and distinctiveness are key components of bringing about change (Dam & Siang, 2020). Businesses with a culture that welcomes new knowledge are eager to test out novel business strategies and see change as an essential component of their operations. Leaders, supervisors and managers must build a working atmosphere that is ready to embrace change by inspiring their subordinates and giving them the advantages of such change and expressing their vision about the business (Carpio, 2018).

Municipal managers who serve as heads of administrative departments in local government must have a deeper awareness of their organisational culture and the ecological condition of their towns to adapt to modern advances rapidly and foresee imminent adjustments (Guillen, 2020). Additionally, recruiting powerful change leaders and fostering a feeling of urgency for change by having an honest and persuasive conversation about what is happening in the community are two ways to bring about change in an organization (Hoholm, 2021). Throughout the organisation, they should establish a vision for transformation. The workforce must be persuaded that change is both important and achievable, and that they can achieve quick wins by setting short-term goals, removing potential roadblocks, and gaining momentum to implement change.

Promotes Organisational Learning

For comprehensive organisational learning to occur, there is a need for rapid reaction by assessing and handling information within the company as well as in its external setting (Dam & Siang, 2020). Sensible mistakes are viewed as opportunities for learning and skill development in an organization with a learning culture. Learning includes gathering experience from achievements and failures. A learning organization welcomes innovation and leadership that sees change not as a single event, but as a continual process (Jensen, 2020). Change is incorporated into the very foundation of organisations as part of their continuing existence and constant evolution. As a result, HRM plays a critical role in fostering an innovative culture together with ongoing education, upskilling, and the acquisition of additional skills pertinent to the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Armstrong & Brown, 2019).

Information and Technology

Innovation in technology can simply be seen as a continuing process

of understanding and sense-building. To understand the intricacy and interconnection of a cognitive process, one must possess specific mental skills and aptitude (Diebolt & Hippe, 2019). The digital and technological networks have frequently been regarded as a significant engine of innovation. Accordingly, it is highly crucial that HRM in any organisation maintains ahead with state-of-the-art technology improvement for it to continue being applicable and meet the demand for provision of services from its citizens' inexhaustible wants (Lema, Kraemer-Mbula, & Rakas, 2021). Leading HRM implies innovation as unavoidable and demands usage of up-to-date technology and relies upon innovative HRM tactics and study findings to develop a culture of innovation.

Furthermore, HRM should adopt technology and abandon the antiquated methods of carrying out their duties (Plantinga, 2021). For instance, during recruiting, several government organizations in South Africa continue to require prospective employees to personally drop off their completed applications or mail them by postal services like couriers. The current age is calling for local governments to move toward e-HRM, which utilizes tools like Microsoft Office 365's Share-Point, MS Teams, and other cutting-edge means of conveying knowledge concerning innovation, job descriptions, performance assessment, rewards, training and development throughout the organisation (Koziol-Nadolna, 2020).

Emphasises Customer Focus

Customer focus, according to Kostakis and Tsagarakis (2022), is a set of values that prioritize the interests of customers while taking into account those of all other stakeholders, including owners, managers, and employees, in order to create long-term objectives. The degree to which management and staff prioritize customer satisfaction and customer service over cost reduction is known as focus on customers (Sicakyuz, 2023). An organizational culture that consistently looks for new and creative methods to satisfy customer expectations and acknowledges the importance of serving both internal and external consumers is essential. In this perspective, the customer is the regular citizen who is the intended recipient of the service being provided. According to Opalka (2021), culture should be incorporated into HRM strategies and utilized throughout orientation workshops to inform new hires that the organization's efforts and innovation should be focused on customer satisfaction.

Method

Data for this study was collected using qualitative methods, focusing on interviews and document analysis.

Participants

The sample contained 2 senior managers who were selected in terms of Section 53 and 56 of the Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000, then additional participants included 8 officials from HRM HRD, HRL and HR Wellness departments. These participants were selected based on their experience and involvement in innovation projects and HRM practices within municipalities. These two senior managers were selected because, according to section 53 the Municipal Manager is the accounting official who is in charge of municipal administration and financial approval. Since the other senior manager designated under Section 56 is directly answerable to the municipal manager, their inclusion in this study is predicated on the vital roles and obligations they perform in the municipality's daily operations.

Procedure

The study participants were categorized using the following codes Participant A- J. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain insights into the challenges faced by the BCMM in fostering innovation. The data obtained from key informant interviews were analysed using thematic data analysis techniques. Initially, the data sets were transcribed from audio clips collected during the interviews into Microsoft Word format. A rigorous set of processes, such as data reduction, categorization, and theme and subtheme identification, was applied to the transcribed data (Bhasin, 2020). The University of Fort Hare's Research Ethics Committee provided an ethical clearance certificate with reference number IJE071 SMUT01.

Results and Discussion

The study's findings showed that HRM at BCMM in the Eastern Cape is encountering a number of challenges when establishing an innovative culture in the municipality.

Resource Constraints

One of the biggest obstacles to innovation is the lack of funding. HRM employees at the BCMM are generally insufficiently supported, with limited funding for training, recruiting, and the adoption of new technologies (BCMM Draft IDP, 2022/23). This has led to a reliance on antiquated techniques and insufficient upskilling initiatives. According to one participant:

"The shortage of funds is an enormous obstacle to the successful implementation of innovation in BCMM. The municipality's ability to support vital HR operations including hiring, training, and technology adoption, all of which are crucial for fostering innovation is directly impacted by a lack of money (Participant A)."

Participant B mentioned that:

"Innovation needs an adept and agile personnel. Yet, as HRM, we are frequently unable to commit appropriate resources for training initiatives due to restricted funding. Without continual growth in knowledge and training, personnel may lack the requisite skills and expertise to adopt new technology or creative practices. This contributes to dependence on obsolete methods and processes, inhibiting attempts to transform and increase efficiency."

Participant E bemoaned that:

"The search for talent with the skills and capabilities required to stimulate innovation is another area that is affected by shortages of resources. Many municipalities in the Eastern Cape do not have the funds to offer competitive salaries or benefits, which limits their ability to attract individuals with the right qualifications and experience in technology, innovation management, or leadership. BCMM is not immune to this challenge as well and this skills gap is hampering its ability to spearhead innovation initiatives."

Given the above excerpt, it can be deduced that the implementation of modern HR technologies, such as automated recruitment platforms, digital performance management systems, or innovative workflow tools, is often delayed or ignored due to cost concerns. It is essential to be aware that innovation does not happen with any cost attached to it, thus, HRM in their planning and budgeting they have to factor in financial resources needed to

achieve that innovation (Mutangabende, Ncube, Mago, Hofisi, & Musara, 2022). Without investment in these technologies, HRM departments are forced to rely on manual processes that are not conducive to innovation or efficiency (Attour & Chaupain-Guillot, 2020). This slows down critical functions and impedes the development of innovative strategies.

Resistance to Change

Many employees and senior officials are resistant to new ways of working. Organizational inertia, fear of job loss due to automation, and scepticism about the value of innovation contribute to slow adoption (Houtgraaf, 2023). Leadership that is averse to risk-taking further exacerbates this resistance. Participant C mentioned that:

"Resistance to change is a critical barrier to innovation within the BCMM HRM department. Despite the recognized need for modernization and efficiency, many employees and senior officials resist new methods, technologies, and organizational structures".

Participant H supported the above idea:

"Municipalities often operate within deeply entrenched systems and cultures that are resistant to transformation. BCMM has long-standing bureaucratic practices and rigid hierarchical structures that create organizational inertia, and as employees, we are accustomed to established routines and we perceive changes as unnecessary or disruptive. This mindset slows the adoption of innovative practices, making it difficult for HRM department to introduce new technologies or processes that could improve efficiency".

Participant F pointed out that:

"Automation and digitalization are key components of innovation, but they often trigger fear among employees. As workers, especially those in administrative or routine-based roles, we are sometimes worried that the adoption of new technologies will make our jobs redundant. This fear of displacement fosters resistance to innovation, as employees we deliberately avoid learning new systems or resist the introduction of automation tools, believing that these changes threaten our job security".

From the above views, it can be deduced that many employees and officials are sceptical about the practical benefits of innovation. There is a perception that innovative initiatives may be costly, difficult to implement, or unlikely to produce tangible improvements in service delivery (Danielle & Masilela, 2020). This scepticism can stem from previous failed attempts at introducing new systems or a lack of understanding about the potential positive impacts of innovation (Armstrong & Brown, 2019). Consequently, personnel can fail to be motivated to embrace innovative ideas, perceiving them as unneeded disturbances rather than possibilities for development.

Skills Shortages

There is a significant scarcity of talented professionals who can promote and manage innovation in BCMM and South Africa in particular. HRM at BCMM struggles to attract and retain personnel with the requisite digital and managerial capabilities to spearhead innovative initiatives. Inadequate internal training programs and a dearth of chances for ongoing professional growth exacerbate this problem (Koziol-Nadolna & Beyer, 2021).

"A serious lack of qualified employees creates an essential

obstacle to the rollout of innovation in BCMM," stated participant A. To spur innovation and enhance service delivery, the contemporary public sector requires a staff with specialized digital, managerial, and strategic skills. But BCMM's HR department finds it difficult to draw in, keep, and nurture such talent."

Participant D stated that:

HRM faces difficulties in attracting individuals with the necessary skills in digital technology, innovation management, and leadership. The majority of local governments in the Eastern Cape often struggle to keep up with the corporate world or more developed municipalities with regard to compensation packages, professional progression prospects, or access to resources. As a result, individuals with the expertise required to lead innovation initiatives are often drawn to other sectors or regions, leaving municipalities with a limited talent pool".

Another participant noted that:

"Innovation in municipalities is closely tied to the adoption of digital technologies, such as e-governance platforms, automated HR processes, and data analytics. However, our municipality is facing a critical shortage of employees with the technical skills to implement and manage these technologies. This gap hinders HRM department from leveraging technology to streamline operations, improve service delivery, and introduce more efficient management systems" (Participant H).

From the above verbatim, the existing training and development programs within HRM departments are often outdated and insufficient to address the evolving needs of a workforce tasked with driving innovation. Without structured programs to enhance employees' digital, managerial, and strategic skills, HRM in BCMM struggles to build the internal capacity needed to implement innovative initiatives (Mariani, Eggers, Chew, & O'Leary, 2021). Moreover, the absence of continuous learning opportunities means that even the existing workforce is not being adequately prepared for the challenges of a modern, innovation-driven public sector (Medley, 2020). Additionally, the lack of IT proficiency among existing staff slows the pace of digital transformation, as many employees are unprepared to work in increasingly digitalized environments.

Outdated Policies and Systems

Outdated policies and systems significantly hinder the ability of HRM in BCMM to foster innovation. Modern work environments, characterized by flexibility, technological integration, and adaptive processes, require policies and systems that can support these changes (Shava & Vyas-Doorgapersad, 2022). However, many municipalities are still bound by rigid, bureaucratic frameworks that stifle innovation in several key areas. Participant E openly argued that:

"As HRM, we often operate under policies that are designed for traditional, hierarchical work environments rather than modern, agile organizations. These policies demand rigid hours of work, stringent chains of command, and restrictive performance evaluation standards, all of which inhibit the acceptance of less rigid, innovative techniques. For instance, the regulations that we utilize restrict being physically present at the office, preventing the opportunity for working remotely or hybrid models, which might boost productivity and attract competent workers".

Participant D laments that:

"Our hiring procedures are outmoded and fail to capture the skills needed in a contemporary, innovation-driven government. Rigid certification requirements and drawn-out hiring processes frequently hinder the HRM department's ability to quickly find individuals with managerial and digital competence. These antiquated workforce regulations prioritize tenure over performance, which makes it challenging to develop a flexible, dynamic workforce that can welcome innovation."

Participant A maintained the above impression:

"Performance management system in our municipality is based on outmoded criteria that leave little room for innovation, teamwork, or the use of new technologies. This system focuses on task completion and time-based evaluations, rather than rewarding innovative problem-solving or process improvements. As a result, employees have little incentive to innovate, as their efforts in this area may not be recognized or rewarded by the current system.

Therefore, it can be deduced that BCMM has policies that are not conducive to flexible work arrangements, such as remote work, job-sharing, or flexi time. In the context of an increasingly digital world, the inability to support flexible work models restricts HRM's ability to attract younger, tech-savvy employees who may prefer more adaptable working conditions (Arundel et al., 2019). Without policy updates to support flexibility, HRM in BCMM will continue to be unable to create a work environment that promotes creativity, employee engagement, and productivity (Falconi & Witter, 2021).

Weak Organizational Culture

A weak organizational culture significantly impedes the ability of HRM department in the BCMM to foster innovation. The BCMM operates within a hierarchical culture characterized by rigid structures and traditional practices, which discourage collaboration, creativity, and open communication (Clausen, Demircioglu, Alsos, & 2020). This type of culture presents several challenges that inhibit innovation. Participant K noted the following with concerns:

"The prevalence of hierarchical structures within our municipality creates an environment where decision-making is often centralized at the top. The resulting structure restricts contributions from workers at lower levels who have significant perspectives or unique ideas. Employee disengagement and an unwillingness to share ideas or question the status quo result from this culture, which makes them feel as though their contributions are underappreciated."

Participant A contended that:

"In this municipality, upholding the current state takes precedence, and this frequently leads certain staff members to develop a fear of failure that hinders taking risks and experimenting. When innovation is confronted with scepticism or harsh repercussions, employees are less willing to offer inventive concepts or try out unproven approaches. This fear stifles creativity and undermines a culture of innovation, since some of us may prefer to play it safe instead of risk condemnation or protecting our jobs."

Participant H pointed out that:

"Here, departments function independently rather than cooperatively, and this is the outcome of a weak organizational

culture. In our situation, there is little communication between teams, and staff members are reluctant to interact with coworkers in different areas. This absence of cooperation is impeding the exchange of ideas and reducing the possibility of creative solutions that incorporate a variety of viewpoints and specialties."

A feeble organisational culture frequently fails to acknowledge and reward innovative achievements, as seen by the aforementioned attitudes. It conveys a message that innovation is not valued when workers who take initiative or offer new solutions are not rewarded or acknowledged (Wang, 2023). New innovative methods and ideas are viewed as threats to the status quo (Mutangabende et al., 2022). This lack of recognition can further entrench the status quo and discourage future attempts at innovation. Furthermore, people who prefer the status quo are fearful of change because they are profiting current system and believe that new concepts or methods of carrying out their duties could put their jobs in jeopardy.

Technological Barriers

One major obstacle to innovation is the sluggish adoption of digital tools and technologies. The potential for innovation is limited since the HRM department frequently lacks the technical infrastructure required to implement contemporary hiring, performance management, or training systems (Opalka, 2021). The capacity to update HRM operations and other services, which are crucial for increasing operational efficiency and improving service delivery is hampered by the sluggish adoption of digital tools and technologies. According to Participant L:

"Many municipalities depend upon antiquated both software and hardware systems that are unable to handle cutting-edge human resources management practices." In our situation, the implementation of modern digital solutions for recruiting, managing performance, training, and staff engagement is hampered by this technical shortcoming. Our HRM department cannot use technology to boost staff collaboration and communication or expedite processes without a strong technological backbone."

Participant I asserted that:

"BCMM employees and leadership frequently exhibit opposition to embracing technological advances because of a lack of understanding or fear of change." This reluctance originates from doubts about the efficacy of digital solutions, worries about the intricate nature of new systems, or the possibility of job redundancy due to automation."

Participant J echoed that:

"There is a lack of strategic vision regarding the role of technology in HRM here in BCM and this is leading to ad hoc decisions about technology adoption. There is no clear roadmap for how technology can be leveraged to improve HRM functions, and departments are missing opportunities for innovation because there are no people who are tech-savvy".

From the above views, it can be concluded that there are several challenges impeding innovation in BCMM such as resource constraints, skills shortage, outdated policies and systems, weak organizational culture which seeks to promote the status quo, and technological barriers. Thus, even when new technologies are implemented, resources are still needed for training and incentivizing those who are innovative because lack of adequate

training and support can hinder their effective use (Torfing, 2019). Employees may not receive the necessary training to utilize new HRM systems fully, which can result in frustration and lower adoption rates (Carpio, 2018). The potential advantages of these tools are not realized if staff members are unable to use them efficiently, which restricts creativity and productivity gains.

Discussion

According to the study's findings, the BCMM lacked funding to support innovation. The BCMM's capacity to invest in cutting-edge HR technologies is often hampered by financial limitations. The HRM department is frequently forced by budgetary constraints to put short-term operational requirements ahead of long-term technology developments (Arundel et al., 2019). They might therefore miss out on crucial investments in digital tools that could boost productivity, stimulate innovation, or improve data management. A cycle of underinvestment brought on by a lack of funding may result in a continued reliance on antiquated systems (Dam & Siang, 2020).

Additionally, the results of the study demonstrated that opposition to innovation is made worse by BCMM's lack of extensive change management techniques. Preparing, assisting, and supporting people and organizations as they move from their current to their future states are all part of change management (Danielle & Masilela, 2020). Employees at BCMM feel misinformed or overlooked in decision-making since there is no defined communication plan or framework to lead them through the innovation process. This lack of engagement can heighten resistance to change, as employees feel uncertain or unprepared for new working methods (Gasela, 2022). The scarcity of leaders who understand both public administration and innovation management prevents local governments from fostering an environment that supports creative problem-solving and new approaches to service delivery.

More so, leadership is the cornerstone and foundation upon which the organization establishes procedures, turnaround strategies and actions to improve service delivery through innovation. Mazibuko (2020) asserted that the leader is supposed to develop turnaround plans to ensure that public complaints are addressed through engaging with various stakeholders. The Municipal Systems Act, 53 of 1998, outlines that the Executive Mayor can designate up to ten councillors as political change champions to spearhead service delivery improvement through working with directors and the municipal manager, who is the administrator and accounting officer (Nciweni, 2024). Thus, Groebler and Groebler (2023:7) contend that effective strategy execution requires leadership, not just of the organisation, but also in the organisation, with a focus on strategy alignment with innovation mentoring officials in different departments and making sure that resources are used prudently to support delivering of public services (Douwes, 2018). Leadership is at the centre of shaping how resources are distributed, how a new culture can be accepted, how skills shortages can be addressed and the adoption of new technologies and new ways of doing things in an organisation. As long as leadership is not supporting the turnaround strategies of the organisation including innovation, it means innovation will remain a myth in local government (Trivellato, Martini, & Cavenago, 2021).

The results indicated that skills shortage among employees

in BCMM remains a huge barrier to innovation in the public sector. Employees lacked the essential and relevant skills needed to implement changes in the municipality (Hippe, 2019). Two studies conducted by the Department of Higher Education in 2019 and 2020 by LGSETA supported this assertion as they indicated that South African municipalities are facing a high prevalence of under-qualified staff in critical positions and skills mismatch to drive innovation (Local Government Sector Education & Training Authority, 2025). Innovation come from creative capabilities which needs further development through training and practice, failure to have such skills, innovation will remain a fairy tale. Moreso, results showed that the bureaucratic nature of local government processes delays the implementation of innovation projects in BCMM. HRM is often required to navigate complex layers of approvals and regulatory compliance before any new system or initiative can be introduced (Plantinga, 2021). This slow pace of decision-making discourages experimentation and diminishes the momentum needed to drive innovation. The time it takes to deploy new systems frequently leads to missed opportunities for improvement, even in cases where change is clearly needed (Clausen et al., 2020).

According to the study's findings, the BCMM frequently used antiquated software and manual procedures, which makes it difficult to deploy cutting-edge HR solutions or expedite operations (Wang, 2023). For instance, manual payroll systems and paper-based personnel records are less effective and more prone to mistakes. The department's ability to implement innovations that might greatly enhance its operations is hampered by the absence of streamlined digital platforms for HR services like hiring, performance management, and staff development (Shava & Vyas-Doorgapersad, 2022). It is crucial to emphasize how new technologies upend the bureaucratic status quo, cut expenses, and simplify procedures, thereby empowering residents and rebuilding public confidence in local government (Gina, 2025). In addition to measuring the impact of creativity and motivating staff to embrace innovation, embracing digitalization helps with data analytics to identify areas that need more improvement. This can also involve identifying committed individuals to spearhead innovation efforts (Dlamini, Plantinga, Davids, Ayodele, Sanchez, & Dlamini, 2024).

The study's findings demonstrated that BCMM frequently lacked the structures and resources necessary to offer its staff Continuous Professional Development (CPD). The CPD is essential for keeping up with technological advances, new management approaches, and innovative public sector practices (Dam & Siang, 2020). However, budgetary constraints and a lack of strategic focus on skill-building have led to gaps in opportunities for staff to upgrade their skills over time. This lack of ongoing development stifles innovation, as employees are not equipped with the latest knowledge and tools needed to innovate effectively (Gasela, 2022).

Conclusion

Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality is confronted by a number of obstacles while implementing innovation, especially in the area of human resource management. The municipality's capacity to successfully implement and maintain new practices is hampered by a number of issues, including employee reluctance to change, low digital literacy, inadequate training, and limited resources. These challenges are further compounded by an organizational culture that is reluctant to adopt new concepts and a lack of leadership involvement. Improving service delivery and increasing

organizational efficiency depend on addressing these issues. HRM and the entire leadership must work together, pool their resources, and foster an innovative culture to modernize and improve service delivery. If this is not done, the municipality will keep falling behind and residents will continue experiencing inadequate services, which will eventually result in service delivery protests, infrastructure damage, and other losses. Therefore, the obstacles HRM faces in BCMM can be solved with a proactive strategy that includes leadership commitment, focused training, technological advancement, and cultivating an innovative culture. By addressing these problems directly, the municipality can unleash its creative potential and build a more proactive and nimble local government that can adapt to the changing needs of its residents.

Recommendations

A number of specific ideas can be put into practice to enhance innovation within BCMM.

Note. Source: Compiled by the Authors

Leadership Engagement

It is commended that BCMM senior executives actively support innovation by exhibiting dedication and receptivity to novel concepts. Promoting a culture of experimentation, learning, and measured risk-taking helps lessen top-level resistance.

Upskilling and Reskilling Programs

It is advised that the BCMM fund continue education initiatives aimed at giving current staff members the managerial and digital skills required for innovation. This covers instruction in data analytics, project management, new technology, and leadership. An organized learning and development program will guarantee that staff members can continue to adjust to new developments.

Policy Modernization

It is advised that the BCMM collaborate with senior leadership to examine and update out-of-date policies in order to better fit contemporary, adaptable work settings. This could entail implementing regulations that permit remote work, flexible scheduling, and performance-based incentives that honour originality and inventiveness. In order to cut down on bureaucratic delays, the BCMM should also look into simplifying approval procedures. In order to ensure that BCMM is prepared to adjust to technological advancements and a changing environment, it is necessary to update its policies, adopt new ones that are specifically designed to welcome innovations, and foster an innovative culture (SALGA, 2018).

Digitization of HR Systems

The BCMM must make an investment in cutting-edge HR software that can facilitate digital workflows, enhance data management, and automate repetitive chores. Digital platforms for hiring, performance monitoring, and development can boost productivity and free up HRM to concentrate on strategic innovation projects rather than paperwork. To increase citizen participation and service accessibility, online platforms for recruiting and selection, as well as other digital tools must be developed.

Promote the Culture of Open Communication

Fostering an atmosphere that promotes candid communication and constructive criticism is essential to promoting creativity. HRM should organize frequent gatherings, town halls, or forums where staff members may freely express issues, exchange ideas, and participate in conversations regarding innovation and other advancements. Regardless of one's place in the hierarchy, leadership must actively show that all opinions are respected. Fear and scepticism in BCMM can be reduced with open and honest communication about the advantages of innovation and employee participation in decision-making. Employees are more inclined to accept change when they see how innovation can enhance their work and support objectives of the organisation.

Fostering a Culture of Technology Adoption

Leadership should actively promote a culture that embraces technology and innovation. This includes communicating the benefits of new technologies and demonstrating how they can enhance work processes and outcomes. Leaders can also encourage a mindset of continuous improvement and learning among staff, helping to reduce resistance to change.

Further studies can look at the issue of skills shortage versus skills mismatch as a barrier to innovation because some staff members might have certain skills that are useful in one area but still require further training for them to be innovative or at least stimulate innovative ideas in them. Additionally, more research can examine how HRM might foster an innovative culture in municipalities through training and development. Which funding approaches may be applied to finance innovation to guarantee that sufficient resources are set aside or intended for innovation in local government?

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